

Paper 11

STUDY ON THE EVALUATION MECHANISM IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Universities in India are globally famous for providing quality education with low cost. The privatization has further developed formal education with advance technology, infrastructure and learning environment. It has become a matter of pride to show case the innovations they do in providing the best education. Sustainability can be attained only by detecting the defects in teaching, learning and evaluation system of education and finding proper solutions in this regard. The prime stakeholders in education comprises of the students, faculties, staffs, parents, employers, collaborative institutions, regulating bodies, banks, sponsoring bodies etc. The expectation from each set of stakeholder differs in magnitude. Educational Institutions shall establish and adopt Feedback Management System (FMS) to detect the best practices and defects existing in the educational system. The National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) mandates the Feedback from the Stakeholders especially the students. This paper describes the regulatory norms, processes, opportunities, challenges of Feedback Management System in the Higher Education Institutions in India.

Keywords: *Accreditation, Best Practices, Defects, Education, Feedback, Management, Stakeholders, University.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Education plays significant role in improving the living standards of the people. Indian higher education is considered to be the largest educational system in the world. The market economies like Japan, Republic of Korea, Philippines, Colombia etc. are dominated by the

Private Sectors whereas developing countries of South Asia like India, Africa, Western Europe etc follow Mixed system [1]. Privatization enhanced opportunity for the private individuals to establish Schools, Colleges and Private Universities catering to the increasing demand for education [2]. The increasing number of aspirants for higher education has demanded enormous challenges in the management of higher education system [3]. Privatization has become a strategic policy due to the declining public budget and growing social demand for education [4]. There is a need for rapid transformation in the structural mechanisms of educational management systems by bringing changes over the traditional twentieth century educational practices. The Universities should provide quality education with comparatively low cost. The prime stakeholders in education system includes parents who pay the fee, the students who are aspirants of new degree, the teaching faculty who are the service provider at the ground level, the organization which is instrumental in this noble task, the bodies which regulate the educational institutions, alumni's who carry the pride of institution, employers who provide the opportunity to show case the learnt knowledge and skill of the learner, media which exposes the real essence of achievement and lacunas and finally the society at large who intern get benefit through the process of education. The goodwill of an educational institution depends on its service utility towards its stakeholders. It is very essential to understand the crucial role played by the prime stakeholders to achieve sustainability in the quality of educational services. It is very essential to understand that, education is a journey of students and faculties in collaboration with other stakeholders towards achieving absolute literacy and employment.

2. STAKEHOLDER EXPECTATIONS

Every educational institution should try to meet the stakeholder's expectations to attain sustainability. The expectations are not static but dynamic with the time and changes from person to person. Based on the role of each person who interacts with the educational institution his expectation differs. Any unmet expectation will become threat to the institution in the future days. All students in spite of slow learners, average learners or fast learners will expect learner centered education through appropriate teaching and learning pedagogies for gaining more knowledge, skill and experience to enrich their competency. The parents measure the success of their ward through the job they get and the personality they develop in the educational life. As a stakeholder of education, they always expect the best quality education to their ward. Effective teachers can provide varied learning experience to the students through individual and collaborative teaching techniques by using student centric or participatory forms of learning. The National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) has established Student Feedback Policy and included under the scoring pattern for the process of Accreditation. The Management of the Higher Educational Institution both Public and Private will expect for the consistent improvement in the teaching and learning processes. Alumni expect the goodwill of the

institution through advancement and innovations year after the year. Employers are the ultimate purchaser of the finished goods produced by the educational institutions by offering good package. Industries are expecting specialized courses with latest and best industry oriented syllabus so as to get the most employable graduates [5].

3. FEEDBACK MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

The knowledge and skill of the graduates shall be enriched by increasing the productivity of the educational institutions. Education should be sustainable and meet the global standards through quality, affordability and ethics [6]. The assessment of Teaching, Learning and Evaluation processes to introduce reforms to increase efficiency and effectiveness of education system. The evaluation of the education is possible only with the development inductive feedback. The aim of feedback management system is to evaluate the Infrastructure, Teaching, Learning, Curriculum, Pedagogy, Performance, Interaction, Competency, Quality and Good will from the views of Students, Parents, Alumni's, Employer, Management, Governing bodies and public at large. The effective Feedback Management System should have the following features.

(1) Feedback Management Committee: The educational institutions shall constitute feedback management committee comprising of Chairmen and other members to manage the feedback management system of every semester.

(2) Feedback Formats: The feedback from the different stakeholders will be collected through using questionnaire which is prepared by the feedback management committee of the department.

(a) Student Feedback: The Skill and Competency of the teacher depends on their subject knowledge hence teachers having good command over the teaching subject can get positive feedback from the students [7]. The success of education can be witnessed through the communication of teachers and students as the feedback of the students will improve the teachers performance [8].

(b) Teachers Feedback: Teachers shall be encouraged to conduct collaborative research activities along with students and publish the findings with reputed journals would really boost the quest for new ideas among the young scholars.

(c) Alumni's Feedback: The feedback will be based on the industry and academia connection to ensure curriculum and skills in line with the industrial requirements. The Alumni Association should be active to provide assistance in building industry academia interactions by providing

required synergies and linkages to address the prevailing challenges of employment and industrial training to the graduates.

(d) Employer Feedback: There is a need for thorough study and evaluation of industry expectations to work out strategies to adopt in the educational system.

(3) Process of Collecting Feedback: The Feedback can be collected by both physical and virtual modes. Students give feedback through online using a standard designed form. Semantic Web technologies are being applied in recent times with different purposes in Education. The University Grants Commission has issued direction to all the Higher Education Institutions to maintain an Online Platform either in the College Website or by any other mode The Physical Feedback also can be maintained by the institutions. Physical Feedback of the students once in every semester before the semester examination. Parent's feedback can be collected once a year on the day of orientation. Alumni Feedback can be collected through the online sources like mail or Virtual feedback mode once a year or on the day of Convocation. The Employer feedback can be collected during the end of Field Work/ Internship/ Project/Summer Placement/Block Placement.

(4) Record Maintenance: The collected data through the feedback forms need to be properly maintained in the institutions. The confidentiality of the information provider should be safeguarded to encourage true feedbacks on the system. The Feedback Management Committee shall maintain the following documents systematically both in the soft and hard copies. The using of Automated Student Feedback System will reduce the burden of maintaining bulk records and it makes easy the task of feeding, retrieval, updating the feedback details.

(5) Action Plan on Feedback: Feedback Management Committee shall conduct meetings and review all the feedback received through virtual and physical mode. The members shall make a report of the effective suggestions or defects which are notified in the filled in feedback forms. A detailed Report has to be made by the Committee to present it before the Management to discuss avenues for the Improvement.

(6) Correction and Improvement: The action plan on the Feedback should be executed to the management. The Management along with the Chairmen of the Feedback Management Committee shall discuss various issues which are sought in the feedback forms. All the Defects should be identified and forwarded to the concerned head of the department to investigate into the defect and identify measures to correct the defects. If any defects with the Infrastructure have to be taken care by the Management by providing required financial support. Any acts of

negligence, misconduct or any unethical practices notified will be referred to the Grievance Redressal Committee of the University/Institutions to take up further actions.

4. OPPORTUNITIES FOR EXCELLENCE

There is a need to equip with the desired quality and standards in education to transform young generation into productive work force with skill and talent. The quality of the educational services can be ensured in the following ways.

(i) Identify the Best Practices & Defects: The educational institutions shall identify various best practices in teaching and learning by conducting research and try to invest in quality improvement strategies. There is a need for regular revision of curriculum to provide industry based learning by involving experts from different field of study. Due consideration shall also be given to the intensive use of available infrastructural facilities.

(ii) Analyze the System: Each academic institution shall undertake internal and external environmental analysis to analyze the impact of education.

(iii) Transparency: This is the era of Information Technology. The educational system should be inculcated with Information Technology. Educational Institutions should provide intensive attention to analyze student experiences on learning and teaching through Semantic based Automated Feedback System [9]. It shall maintain a transparent system to review feedback through the institutional websites with forum to comment, suggest and direct speculative ways to improve the overall quality of education.

5. CHALLENGES

(a) Financial Constraints: The Public and Private Institutions are facing the financial constraints to invest much on the infrastructure and other facilities. The rigidity in public finance, complexity of financial grants are affecting the private institutions to a great extent.

(b) Mobility: The Teaching fraternity is mobile in the private sector because of variation in the pay scale among the institutions. The teachers with Ph. D and Research experience are very costly hence institutions with financial constraints cannot offer for such teachers.

(c) University Affiliation: The Universities are putting more affiliation charges on the affiliating institutions creating diversion of the funding towards the payment of mandatory costs instead of investment for improving the quality.

6. CONCLUSION

This system helps to identify the stakeholder friendly practices and notify the existing problems in teaching, learning and evaluation processes. The feedback is generally sought from the students, parents, alumni and employers to invite open appraisal and criticisms on the aspects of practices, pedagogies, innovations, changes etc. In this regard, education plays a vital role towards Human Resource Development and empowerment so as to bring National Growth. Education, greatly contributes towards growth of the nation through Human Resource Development and Empowerment. The Industry academia collaborations through joint Research, Internships, Training and Corporate Social Responsibility would help in institutional branding and skill development of the students. It is essential to scale up our effort towards achieving quality in education in the multi fold through feedback management system. In spite of investing in the higher education there is a need to establish world class research facilities, recruitment of eminent academicians into the Universities and Research Institutions. Securing the Best results by the graduates in their final examination cannot be the proof for the Universities for rendering the best education unless seeking the fair feedback over the educational process [10]. The Higher education can improve teaching methods, learning process, syllabus, core and soft subjects, skill development, practical's, experiential learning as per the industry expectations through a systematic Feedback Management System.

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